

On the long-term stability of foams stabilised by mixtures of nano-particles and oppositely charged short chain surfactants

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Abstract

We have studied the foaming properties of aqueous dispersions containing mixtures of silica nanoparticles (Ludox TMA) and a short-chain amphiphile (*n*-amylamine). By combining standard hand shaking methods and microfluidic techniques we show that stable foams can be obtained at amine concentrations above approximately 0.5wt%, which appears to be a critical concentration for cooperative association between particles and amine. In contrast to foams stabilised solely by nanoparticles, these foams suffer from slow coarsening due to gas exchange between bubbles. "Superstable" foams for which coarsening is inhibited can only be produced at sufficiently high particle and amine concentrations (typically 10 and 3wt%, respectively) for which the dispersions also gel in the continuous phase of the foam. We combine investigations of the static and dynamic properties of the particle-laden air-water interfaces in an attempt to elucidate some of the key mechanisms which control the observed behaviour.

1 Introduction

Foams are dispersions of gas bubbles in a liquid phase, stabilised by surface active agents such as surfactants, proteins, polymers or particles. Foams are thermodynamically unstable and exhibit a wide range of characteristic lengths and time scales of evolution. Their stability is therefore inherently difficult to model. The destabilisation of foams is governed by three principal mechanisms: drainage, coarsening and coalescence. ¹ Drainage is the gravity-driven removal of the liquid between bubbles, facilitating not only gas diffusion from smaller to bigger bubbles (coarsening) but also the rupture of thin films separating neighbouring bubbles (coalescence). Much research effort has been successfully put into understanding the physicochemical requirements for the suppression of these instability mechanisms. Drainage can be slowed down by increasing bulk viscosity (and to some extent surface viscosity). ² Coarsening can be reduced using gases of low solubility ³ and by increasing the elastic moduli of the gas-liquid interfaces. ⁴ Increasing surface stiffness also renders foams more stable against coalescence. ⁵

Excellent candidates to simultaneously fight all three destabilisation mechanisms are surface active particles. Although the capability of particles to stabilise foams and emulsions has been known for almost one hundred years ⁶ (and mainly in the industrial domain, such as flotation ⁷ and food processing ⁸), the fundamental understanding of the underlying stabilising mechanism at the scale of individual bubbles or entire foams is much more recent and still incomplete. ^{9–16} The key ingredient in particle-stabilised foams is the high adsorption energy of the particle at the air-water interface which can be approximated as $E_{\text{ads}} = \pi R^2 \gamma_{\text{W}} (1 - \cos \theta)^2$, with R being the particle radius, γ_{W} the surface tension of the air-water interface and θ the contact angle of the particle at the air-water interface measured through the water. ¹⁷ Despite the force balance at particle-laden air-water interfaces being complex and still not completely understood, it is known that the optimal contact angle is below 90° . ^{18,19} A particle with a typical radius of 10 nm and a contact angle of 80° will have an adsorption energy of approximately $10^3 k_{\text{B}} T$ (with k_{B} being the Boltzmann constant and T the absolute temperature), three orders of magnitude higher than that associated with surfactants. ⁹ This leads to an effectively irreversible attachment of the particles to the air-water interface, yielding solid-like surface layers which may prevent both coarsening and coalescence. ^{9–15,20,21} In contrast, particles with contact angles of 90° or higher are known to have antifoaming capacity. ¹⁸

The surfaces of the particles are either modified chemically ¹¹ or through the physisorption of oppositely charged amphiphiles. ^{12,22,23} Due to the ease of preparation and its applicability to very different types of particles and amphiphiles, ^{12,22} physisorption is becoming a popular method for the generation of highly stable foams. The presence of amphiphiles can increase or decrease lifetimes of particle-stabilised foams by affecting particle hydrophobicity, ^{17,24,25} flocculation behaviour, ^{23,26} surface tension ¹² and surface rheology. ^{27–30} Most available studies of this kind of systems combine simple foaming experiments (shaking or mixing) with investigations of the bulk properties and simple surface

tension measurements.^{12,22,23} In the other limit, investigations concentrate on the complex interfacial properties of such mixtures without giving much attention to their foaming capacities.^{30–32} Even though the available studies are beginning to provide an understanding of the key mechanisms which control the stability of foams stabilised by particle-amphiphile mixtures, many questions remain open as to how drainage, coalescence and coarsening of the foams are related to the complex properties of the particle-laden gas-liquid interfaces. This is due to the fact that simple foaming studies through shaking or mixing make it very difficult to disentangle the different mechanisms controlling foam stability.

The present article therefore attempts to shed more light on such questions combining detailed investigations of the interfacial properties of aqueous mixtures of silica nano-particles (Ludox TMA) and *n*-amylamine¹² with well-controlled foaming experiments. *N*-Amylamine is a short chain amphiphile (5 carbon atoms) and therefore highly soluble in water with a high critical micelle concentration, cmc. Its polar head group is an amine, positively charged in aqueous solution, and therefore it is able to adsorb at the negatively charged silica surface through electrostatic interactions depending on the pH ($\text{pH} > \text{p}K_{\text{b}} = 3.37$). In addition, and in contrast to most available studies, neither amine nor particles alone can stabilise foams, facilitating the interpretation of the synergistic effects.¹²

In order to obtain a thorough handle on the interpretation of the foam properties, we generate monodisperse foams³³ using microfluidic techniques.^{34–36} These allow the rapid generation of small and extremely monodisperse bubbles with polydispersities of less than 2%. Observations of the time evolution of such monodisperse foams provide a much clearer picture of the different destabilising mechanisms due to the traceability of monodispersity and average bubble sizes.^{37,48} Moreover, in using purpose-designed microfluidic devices, the mixing process of the chemicals and the concentration ratio between them can be controlled by changing flow rates of liquids. The fact that each bubble is generated one by one in the microfluidic device and under the same conditions provides a very accurate access to concentration and time-dependent foam properties. By combining simple hand shaking with the microfluidic foam experiments we were able to identify different regimes of foam stability, which are described in Section 3. In order to elucidate the key parameters leading to these different regimes, we also investigate the bulk (Section 4) and interfacial properties (Section 5) of the dispersions. We discuss the relevance of bulk and surface properties to foaming and foam stability in each regime in Section 6.

The silica- *n*-amylamine system has been proposed by Gonzenbach and Gauckler¹² who used very large particle concentrations (35 wt%). They obtained foams stable against coarsening, coalescence and even drainage. They associated foam superstability with the synergistic effect of particles and amine on surface tension, mentioning the possible importance of bulk gelation. We show in this paper that coarsening stops when the bulk gelation starts. This could, however, be a coincidence and one still needs to understand the exact balance between bulk and surface contributions.

2 Experimental section

2.1 Materials

LUDOX® TMA colloidal silica nanoparticles (34wt% dispersion in H₂O, $\rho = 1.23 \text{ g mL}^{-1}$, specific surface area = $140 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and *n*-amylamine (purity of 99%, $\rho = 0.752 \text{ g mL}^{-1}$) were purchased from Sigma and used without further purification. Highly deionized water obtained from a Milli-Q unit (resistivity of $18.2 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}$, organic content lower than 2 ppb) was used for diluting the commercial particle dispersion and for preparing the *n*-amylamine solution. The initial concentrations of both components used in foam production by microfluidics were 20 and 15wt%, respectively, their mixture and dilution taking place in situ, as described in the Methods section 2.2.

For the other experiments the mixed solution was prepared as follows: *n*-amylamine was dissolved in Milli-Q water in the range of concentrations 0.1 – 10wt%; the adequate volume of the commercial silica nano-particle dispersion was later poured into the corresponding amine solution yielding nano-particle concentrations in the range 1 – 10wt%. Particles were dropped into the amine solution instead of the contrary to avoid high local concentrations of amine that would lead to eventual particle flocculation.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Microfluidics. As sketched in Fig. 1, monodisperse foams stabilised by silica nano-particle- *n*-amylamine mixtures (10wt% particles and increasing concentrations of *n*-amylamine in the range 0 – 3wt%) were generated bubble by bubble within a homemade microfluidic device. Three syringe pumps allow for controlling the particle- *n*-amylamine ratio and absolute concentration: the first one containing a particle dispersion at 20wt%, the second one a *n*-amylamine solution at 15wt% and the third one Milli-Q water to properly dilute the system. A fourth syringe pump is used to control the air flow injected. The liquid and air flows, Q_1 and Q_g , have been fixed to 40 and 60 mL h⁻¹, respectively. The experiment was designed as follows: the aqueous amine solution is mixed with the water coming from the third syringe before mixing with the particle dispersion. The mixing takes place in a tube (1.6 mm diameter) before going into the capillary as schematically illustrated in Fig. 1a. The liquid encounters the air in a T-junction after a delay line of approximately 15 cm (including tube and capillary lengths) to ensure homogeneous mixing of the particle suspension and the amine solution, thus producing highly monodisperse bubbles as shown in the optical microscope image of Fig. 1b. The foamability and stability of the system at increasing *n*-amylamine concentration was studied by filling vials during a fixed period of time (45 s) and by filming individual layers of bubbles for better visibility.

2.2.2 pH measurements. The pH of the silica nanoparticle- *n* amylamine dispersions is measured using a standard pH -meter at room temperature in order

to estimate the amount of base consumed through the dissociation reaction of silanol groups as detailed in Appendix 1.

2.2.3 Size and ζ -potential measurements. The size and ζ -potential of aqueous dispersions of SiO₂ nano-particles at 1wt% and increasing concentration of *n*-amylamine in the range between 0 and 2wt% are measured using a particle analyser instrument (Beckman Coulter - DelsaTM Nano C) at 25°C. The characteristic particle or aggregate hydrodynamic radius assuming a spherical shape has been obtained by using CONTIN. This average value should be taken with caution since it requires the input of the scattering power variation with respect to aggregate size that is not known a priori. Particle ζ -potential is calculated from the measured electrophoretic mobility applying the procedure of ref. 39. As the samples are evolving in time the measurements were done within 2 hours of mixing the particles and the *n*-amylamine to be able to compare the short term properties of the solutions between the different sample concentrations.

2.2.4 Surface tension and surface rheology measurements. Surface tensions γ are measured using a rising bubble tensiometer (Teclis, France). In this method the surface tension is calculated by image analysis from the shape of a bubble using the Laplace equation. We measure the dynamic surface tension γ as a function of time and we define γ_0 as the stationary value of the surface tension when the adsorption is completed and γ no longer changes. Thus we determine γ and γ_0 of pure *n*-amylamine solutions as a function of concentration in the range 0 – 10 wt% and the effect of particle addition for 1 and 10wt% particles. For the particle- *n*-amylamine suspensions the measurements are performed immediately after mixing. Initial volumes for bubbles vary from 3 to 9 μ L and we use volume feedback control for the measurements.

We use the same apparatus for surface-rheological measurements; the surface compression viscoelastic modulus E^* is obtained by performing controlled oscillatory variations of bubble volume at constant and low frequency ($f = 0.2$ Hz) during adsorption. For harmonic perturbations of the surface area A , the viscoelastic modulus E^* is directly evaluated from the amplitude and phase lag ϕ of the surface tension response, which can be written as

$$E^* = \frac{d\gamma}{d \ln A} = E e^{i\phi}$$

We use a Langmuir trough NIMA 602BAM (NIMA Technology, U.K.) to measure the surface pressure Π - area A isotherms of the particle-amine mixtures upon compression and expansion, after γ_0 is achieved. The compression/expansion cycles were performed at a constant velocity of 10 cm² min⁻¹. The surface pressure was measured with a Wilhelmy plate (Whatman CHR 1 chromatography paper, effective perimeter 21 mm supplied by NIMA), which ensures zero contact angle, positioned parallel to the compression. The Langmuir trough is adapted to the Brewster angle microscope.

2.2.5 Brewster angle microscopy. The surface textures of the surface films

formed by the adsorption of the silica nano-particles- *n*-amylamine mixtures are visualized with a MiniBAM (NanofilmTechnologie GmbH, Göttingen, Germany). The setup consists of a laser diode (30 mW and 660 nm), which produces a nearly linear polarized beam ($p/s = 100/1$), sent onto the aqueous phase with an angle of $52 - 54^\circ$, ensuring Brewster's condition, which means no reflection for an ideally sharp interface. The presence of an ultrathin film results in a small reflected intensity (typically, 10^{-6} times the incident beam intensity), but sufficient to detect the eventual presence of domains in the film, due to their different refractive indices. The images were recorded using a CCD camera (60 Hz). In order to filter the residual s-component background, a *p*-positioned analyzer is placed just before the CCD camera. The resolution of such an imaging system is below $20\mu\text{m}$ and the field of view, which exhibits very low geometrical distortion, is $4.8 \times 6.4\text{mm}^2$.

3 Foaming behaviour of silica nano-particle - *n*-amylamine mixtures

We first performed a simple foam stability study by hand shaking the mixed particle-amine dispersions. Images of the foam samples just after shaking ("foamability") and 24 hours later ("foam stability") are shown in Fig. 2 for different particle concentrations c_p (1, 5 and 10wt%) and amine concentrations c_a (between 0 and 10wt%). As observed in many other investigations of similar systems,^{12,22,23} the mixtures foam within a welldefined range of amine concentrations. Without the addition of amine, the particles are too hydrophilic to stabilise foams. With increasing c_a the particles are rendered increasingly hydrophobic and therefore act as foam stabilisers. Around the cmc of the amine, a double layer begins to form around the particles, rendering them increasingly hydrophilic, hence reducing their foaming capacity. These phenomena are also reflected in the bulk properties of the mixtures, in which strong aggregation is observed close to the cmc and redispersion of particles for amine concentrations much higher than the cmc. This is discussed in more detail in Section 4.

Dispersions containing low concentrations of particles, typically $c_p = 1\text{wt}\%$, generate quite stable liquid foams until *n*-amylamine concentrations of approximately 2 – 3wt%. This amine concentration is approximately the same for the higher particle concentrations, which suggests that the important parameter here is c_a rather than the c_a/c_p ratio. Above $c_a = 2 - 3\text{wt}\%$, the dispersions do not foam and bulk phase separation is observed as shown in Fig. 2.

A more quantitative evaluation of the foamability was achieved by measuring the foam height just after foam formation. The variation of foam height with amine concentration c_a for $c_p = 1\text{wt}\%$ is shown in Fig. 3.

The relative change in foam height as a function of time can be considered as an indication of foam stability. We observe no significant change during the first 210 min after foam generation in the whole foaming region (data not shown). However at longer times foams generated from mixtures containing $c_a < 0.5\text{wt}\%$

have almost disappeared while the ones at higher c_a have only slightly reduced their height.

Analysing properties of foams made by hand shaking is quite complex, since there is limited control on the procedure. We have therefore used microfluidics (Section 2.2.1) in the following. In this case, every bubble is generated under the same conditions and a change of monodispersity with time allows us to easily monitor coalescence and coarsening. For reasons which we do not fully understand, we were not able to create foams in the microfluidic device with particle volume fractions lower than 5wt%. This is probably due to the fact that for low particle concentrations the interface is not covered sufficiently during the generation of the foam to stabilise the bubbles when they come into contact at the outlet of the device. Since, at these particle concentrations, it takes about a micro-second for enough particles to diffuse to the interface to reach full coverage, mechanisms other than diffusion may play a role. One possible reason could be the presence of electrostatic barriers⁴⁰ or long rearrangement times of particles at the interface. We have therefore used higher particle concentrations ($c_p = 5$ and 10wt%). Moreover, we could not use amine concentrations larger than 3wt%, because the capillaries were blocked by the particle aggregates formed rapidly above this concentration (see Section 4).

Results of the microfluidic foam generation are summarised in Fig. 4. As for foams made by hand shaking, the foamability in the microfluidic device increases with *n*-amylamine content until $c_a = 0.5\text{wt}\%$. In contrast, the quantity of foam generated remains essentially constant at higher amine concentrations as shown in Fig. 4b. We believe this difference to be due to a nonnegligible increase in viscosity upon aggregation of the particles. In hand shaking experiments such an increase reduces foam generation, whilst the bubble generation in the flow-ratecontrolled microfluidic device remains insensitive to the viscosity over a wide range of viscosities.³⁴ Foam stability is commonly characterised by the "half life time" $\tau_{1/2}$ for which the foam height decreases by 50%. $\tau_{1/2}$ here is observed to increase up to $c_a \sim 0.5\text{wt}\%$, after which it remains constant until it reaches $c_a \sim 2.5\text{wt}\%$. Close to this latter value foams are becoming superstable, for example $\tau_{1/2} > 95$ h for $c_a > 2\text{wt}\%$. Some of these foams are still stable after 2 years without any noticeable change in bubble size. Since the amount of liquid in each bottle is the same, one also notices that the foams maintain a lot more liquid in this range, which is due to a blockage of drainage. Note that we could not make quantitative measurements for the handmade foams, because the amount of foam created was too small. However, the general observations concerning the foam stability follow the same trends.

In order to identify the different phenomena which destabilise the foams we performed further observations of individual bubble layers of initially monodisperse bubbles under a microscope. The observations are summarised in the diagram of Fig. 5. Monodisperse foams generated at low *n*-amylamine concentrations ($c_a < 0.5\text{wt}\%$) evolve by coalescence in the collection tube yielding polydisperse foams and less quantity of foam (see Fig. 4a). For larger amine concentrations ($c_a \sim 1\text{wt}\%$), but small particle concentration (5wt%) "limited coalescence"⁴⁰ is observed (Fig. 5, top left). This limited coalescence occurs

when the bubble surfaces are not sufficiently covered by particles. Upon coalescence, the surface to volume ratio of the created bubbles decreases and hence the surface concentration of the particles increases. Coalescence proceeds until the surface is sufficiently covered, leading to a range of different bubble shapes⁴¹ since the shape relaxation is blocked when the surface layers are sufficiently rigid.⁴² In our case, the final shapes tend to be ellipses. Beyond this stage, foam destabilisation occurs via coarsening only.

For higher particle and amine concentrations (middle row of Fig. 5) the interfaces seem to be covered sufficiently so that coalescence is completely suppressed, giving rise to a perfectly monodisperse foam. However, after sufficiently long waiting times, these bubbles (and therefore the foams) disappear through coarsening. This is shown in a time sequence of images in Fig. 5, middle right. Upon further increasing c_a until $c_a = 3\text{wt}\%$, both coalescence and coarsening are fully suppressed for $c_p = 10\text{wt}\%$, as shown in Fig. 5, bottom right. Bulk gelation was observed in this case and could account for the enhanced stability as in other similar systems,²⁶ however the contribution of the bulk as compared to the interfaces in this regime would be needed to fully demonstrate this hypothesis.

It remains now to understand better the role of the particle and amine concentrations on foaming and foam stability. In order to clarify these issues, we present in the following sections studies of the bulk (Section 4) and of the surface (Section 5) behaviour.

4 Bulk behaviour of mixed silica nanoparticle-*n*-amylamine dispersions

The hydrophobicity of particles can be easily modified in aqueous media via interaction with surfactants.²⁵ Inspired by previous work,¹² we chose *n*-amylamine as the adequate amphiphile to interact with silica surfaces, mainly due to its short carbon chain, i.e. its high critical micelle concentration, and its positively charged head group which is attracted to the negatively charged silica nanoparticle surface. *N*-Amylamine behaves as a base in aqueous solution ($\text{p}K_b = 3.37$), promoting silanol dissociation reaction at the silica nano-particle surface⁴³

This dissociation yields two charged species in dispersion, i.e. $\text{NH}_3^+(\text{CH}_2)_4\text{CH}_3$ and SiO^- , which increases the negative charge of the silica particles.

We measured the pH of silica nano-particle dispersions of different concentrations ($c_p = 1, 5$ and $10\text{wt}\%$) with increasing *n*-amylamine content (from $c_a = 0.1$ to $5\text{wt}\%$). As shown in Appendix 1, at a given c_a , the pH is smaller than for the pure amine solution, evidencing a significant consumption of *n*-amylamine relative to the blanks ($c_p = 0\text{wt}\%$); the higher the particle concentration the higher the *n*-amylamine consumption. When the pH values are

plotted versus c_a/c_p , no scaling is observed (inset of Fig. 10). This means that the association between particles and amine is not purely electrostatic. This is discussed in more detail in Appendix 1.

We also measured the zeta-potential of the particles as a function of *n*-amylamine concentration in the hours following mixing. A diluted dispersion of silica nanoparticles ($c_p = 1\text{wt}\%$) is used to determine the initial particle surface charge ($\zeta = -56\text{ mV}$) as shown in Fig. 6a. The average values of the hydrodynamic particle diameter d_h are also measured by light scattering as shown in Fig. 6b. Since the scattering power variation with respect to aggregate size is not obvious and is needed as an input for CONTIN analysis, the displayed values should be taken with caution. Unfortunately, these determinations could not be made at larger particle concentration due to the turbidity of the solutions. The particle distribution has a peak for a particle diameter of 31 nm, consistent with literature data,^{44,45} and is rather broad (polydispersity index ~ 0.6). This could be due to the presence of small aggregates of primary particles. Interestingly, we found that the zeta potential starts to decrease noticeably only above $c_a^* \sim 0.5\text{wt}\%$ with a noticeable onset of aggregation ($d_h \sim 500\text{ nm}$). Significant flocculation starts above $c_a^{**} \sim 2\text{wt}\%$.

It is well-known that the addition of an acid to silica nanoparticles decreases their surface charge and that the isoelectric point where the particle is neutral is at a pH slightly lower than 3. In contrast, an alkali increases the negative charge of the particles.⁴⁶ This is clearly not the observed trend here: small quantities of *n*-amylamine ($c_a < c_a^* \sim 0.5\text{wt}\%$) maintain particle charge essentially constant while higher *n*-amylamine content ($c_a > c_a^*$) reduces zeta-potential and thus particle charge (Fig. 6) until the force preventing particle flocculation disappears and phase separation is observed (Fig. 2). Such an observed trend can be easily explained considering the double nature of *n*-amylamine: the head group of *n*-amylamine is a base, thus it promotes silanol dissociation, increasing particle charge but at the same time it is a surfactant that adsorbs at the particle surface, neutralising particle charge. Here clearly, the amine adsorption effect dominates. Below $c_a^* = 0.5\text{wt}\%$, the size of the aggregates is slightly larger than in the amine-free dispersions (Fig. 6b), which can be attributed to the presence of surfactant molecules adsorbed at the particle surface and to some aggregates of primary particles already present in the case of amine-free dispersions (PDI ~ 0.7). Above $c_a = 0.5\text{wt}\%$ the particle surfaces become more covered, decreasing ζ and thus system stability. The size of the aggregates significantly increases and their size distribution becomes very polydisperse.

The results therefore confirm that *n*-amylamine adsorb at the particle surface through electrostatic binding, producing in situ particle hydrophobization, which is responsible for the observed foam stabilisation (Fig. 2 and 4). The amine concentration $c_a^* \sim 0.5\text{wt}\%$ is probably a "critical aggregation concentration" (cac) above which adsorption becomes cooperative, i.e. the probability for an amine molecule to adsorb on a site adjacent to another amine already adsorbed is larger than the probability to adsorb randomly.^{22,23,47} This type of cooperative adsorption for cationic surfactants on silica seems to occur at high ionic strengths as in the dispersions studied here.⁴⁷

When the amine concentration increases above $c_a^{**} \sim 2 - 3 \text{ wt\%}$, the mixed dispersion phase separates (Fig. 2). The zeta potential reaches values of the order of 30 mV, still rather repulsive (Fig. 6a). However, particle aggregation can be enhanced by the formation of amine micelles (the cmc is around 2.5wt%, see Section 5), which could give rise to attractive depletion interactions between particles.^{22,48} The maximum foam stability is observed just before phase separation. In such a case, the particle layers at the air-water interface become quite thick, due to limited solubility of the aggregates as in solutions of nonionic surfactants close to the cloud point.⁴⁹ These thick layers could stabilise bubbles against coalescence and coarsening. The fact that the foams become unstable beyond the precipitation boundary could be due to the antifoam action of the nuclei of the particle rich phase which separates out, again as in the case of nonionic solutions above the cloud point.⁵⁰

Above $c_a = 5\text{wt\%}$ the particles re-disperse in the bulk, the samples becoming more transparent (Fig. 2) with long-term stability if particle concentrations are sufficiently low and amine concentrations sufficiently high. Thus, we can define a new critical surfactant concentration, c_a^{***} , which would correspond to the formation of a bilayer at the nanoparticle surface.⁴⁷ In this third region, i.e. $c_a > c_a^{***}$, the particle surface is re-hydrophilised and thus it yields more stable dispersions. The foaming properties are however lost because particles are too hydrophilic as in the absence of amine.²² The dispersions are quite stable but phase separate at very long times (i.e. 5 days, but faster close to c_a^{**} as shown in Fig. 11 in Appendix 2), possibly due to the weak character of the electrostatic binding between *n*-amylamine molecules and silica nanoparticle surfaces.

Therefore, the suggested scenario for $c_p = 1\text{wt\%}$ can be summarized as follows: (1) $c_a < c_a^* \sim 0.5\text{wt\%}$: low particle surface coverage and thus low foam stability, (2) $c_a^* < c_a < c_a^{**} \sim 2.5\text{wt\%}$: more complete particle surface coverage and free surfactant molecules in solution screening particle charge and producing slow particle aggregation which seems to be responsible for the enhanced foam stability, (3) $c_a^{**} < c_a < c_a^{***} \sim 5\text{wt\%}$: faster aggregation of particles, possibly enhanced by the presence of micelles in bulk causing a fast depletion phase separation, both suppressing the capability of the solution to foam and (4) $c_a > c_a^{***}$: bilayer formation at the particle surface causing particle re-dispersion in bulk but making them again so strongly hydrophilic that solutions do not foam. The behaviour of the mixture at the high particle concentration limit ($c_p = 10\text{wt\%}$) is quite similar, except for $c_a > 3\text{wt\%}$ where the dispersions gel and the particle-stabilised foams are superstable ($\tau_{1/2} \sim \text{months}$).

5 Surface behaviour of silica nano-particle - *n*-amylamine mixtures

The following synergistic effects of surfactant-particle mixtures have been previously reported to be crucial for foam stability:^{12,15,22} (1) intermediate particle hydrophobicity, (2) decrease in surface tension and (3) promotion of particle

surface networks. The bulk behaviour of the mixture described in the previous section confirmed the change in particle hydrophobicity caused by the addition of a surfactant. However further insights into all three synergistic effects can be obtained from surface measurements.

Immediately after mixing the particle suspension with the amine solution we measure the dynamic surface tension γ as a function of time using the rising bubble technique (Section 2.2.4) and we determine the stationary surface tension value γ_0 as the value for which adsorption is completed and γ no longer changes. The results are shown in Fig. 7a. The critical micelle concentration cmc of *n*-amylamine is found at approximately 2.5 wt%. The surface tension is not measurably varied upon addition of 1wt% particles. In this case surfactant molecules are removed from the bulk phase due to particle coverage, the others remaining free in solution. It is very difficult to estimate the actual bulk surfactant concentration but it should be certainly lower than in the absence of particles. This should lead to a higher surface tension, and since the tension is actually lower, at least for $c_p = 10\text{wt}\%$, we can conclude, at least in this case, that there are particles at the interface from Fig. 7a. As shown and discussed further below, compression of the interfacial layer in a Langmuir trough evidences clearly the presence of particles in or at least close to - the air-water interface, even for $c_p = 1\text{wt}\%$.

Upon the addition of more particles ($c_p = 10\text{wt}\%$), the surface tension drops measurably, evidencing clearly a contribution of particle interaction in the interface to the interfacial energy. By using a Langmuir trough coupled with a Brewster angle microscope (BAM) (Section 2.2.5) we observed in this concentration range the formation of thick solid domains at the air-water interface separated by monolayers of particles. BAM images of the typical interfacial texture of an aqueous dispersion of $c_a = 1\text{wt}\%$ and $c_p = 10\text{wt}\%$ with $\gamma = \gamma_0 = 35.4\text{mNm}^{-1}$, i.e. after particle adsorption, are shown in Fig. 7b. Upon compression of the layer the domains merge, yielding a homogeneous solid film. Upon expansion of the layer, the solid layer fractures into separate domains. To prove the solid character of the layer we fractured it using a needle, as shown in the rightmost BAM image of Fig. 7b. However since these solid domains are floating in a fluid environment, the surface layer is not globally solid. As a result, foams produced with these c_a and c_p still coarsen (as previously shown in Fig. 5) though they do not coalesce possibly because such solid domains concentrate between bubbles.⁵¹ These types of solid domains do not form in the low particle concentration limit ($c_p = 1\text{wt}\%$), which correlates with the observed bubble coalescence in the corresponding foams and thus their lower stability.

We also studied the time evolution of the surface tension after rapid generation of a bubble (Section 2.2.4) for 10wt% particle dispersions containing 0.5 and 1wt% amine, as shown in Fig. 8a. The time it takes to reach the stationary value γ_0 is of the order of 100 – 1000 s, i.e. much longer than one would expect from simple diffusion calculations, which give typical relaxation times of the order of milli-seconds at these particle concentrations. Hence, slow relaxation processes must be present within the layer linked to an adsorption barrier or particle rearrangements at the interface, but whose exact nature remains to be

elucidated.

In parallel, we measured the dilational elastic modulus of these interfaces using the oscillating bubble technique at a frequency of 0.2 Hz . The time evolution of the elasticity follows that of the surface tension, as shown in Fig. 8b, but the absolute values remain surprisingly low considering the solid-like nature of the domains visualised in Fig. 7b. This may be due to the fact that the domains seem to be floating in the surface like islands with the overall elasticity of the interface being therefore dominated by the nature of the layer between the domains. It is interesting to note also, that the elasticity decreases upon increasing amine concentration. This is commonly observed upon hydrophilisation of the particles when surfactant bilayers are formed on the particles. This seems to be an unlikely scenario here, as the measured concentrations are far from the cmc . This effect must therefore result from a different interaction between the surfac-tant-laden air-water interface and the surfactant covered particle. No measurable moduli are measured for *n*-amylamine alone during or at the end of the adsorption. As for the amine alone, the surface elastic modulus of the mixtures containing $c_p = 1\text{wt}\%$ is negligible, as expected from the coincidence of the surface tension values (Fig. 7) and from the absence of solid domains at equilibrium.

Further insights into the elastic properties of the mixtures in the low particle concentration limit ($c_p = 1\text{wt}\%$) can be gained from surface pressure Π -surface area A compression isotherms. The compression isotherms of surfactant-particle mixtures containing an increasing *n*-amylamine content, i.e. $c_p = 1\text{wt}\%$ and $c_a = 0.1, 0.5$ and $1\text{wt}\%$ are shown in Fig. 9. The compression is performed after equilibrium is achieved and the measurement is performed with the plate in parallel to the compression. The initial surface pressures are different for the different *n*-amylamine concentrations: the higher the *n*-amylamine concentration, the lower the equilibrium surface tension (Fig. 7) and thus the higher the initial surface pressure ($\Pi_0 = \gamma_w - \gamma_0$). The leftmost panel of Fig. 9 corresponds to the lower *n*-amylamine concentration ($c_a = 0.1\text{wt}\%$) for which a liquid expanded isotherm is obtained in the whole compression range experimentally accessible. The middle panel corresponds to an intermediate *n*-amylamine concentration ($c_a = 0.5\text{wt}\%$). The initial liquid expanded (LE) layer experiences a transition to a liquid condensed (LC) phase, the phase coexistence (LE-LC) plateau being observed at $\Pi_{\text{plateau}} = 29.8\text{mNm}$. . This would correspond to the appearance of solid-like domains as previously reported by Santini et al.²⁹ Further compression leads to the layer collapse and thus multilayer formation as further discussed in Appendix 3: $A_{\text{col}} = 304.6 \text{ cm}^2$ and $\Pi_{\text{col}} = 31.2\text{mNm}^{-1}$. The higher *n*-amylamine concentration ($c_a = 1\text{wt}\%$) is shown in the rightmost panel of Fig. 9. For this concentration, an increase of Π_{col} and Π_{plateau} is observed: $A_{\text{col}} = 333.8 \text{ cm}^2$, $\Pi_{\text{col}} = 40.0\text{mN m}^{-1}$ and $\Pi_{\text{plateau}} = 38.3\text{mNm}^{-1}$. Multilayer formation is irreversible (at least at short times, compression and expansion rates were $10 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ min}^{-1}$) as shown by the hysteretic behaviour of the system upon expansion, the hysteresis being more pronounced for higher *n*-amylamine concentrations.

The observed hysteresis is absent in pure amine surface layers, indicating that some of the adsorbed species are irreversibly adsorbed at the time scales of the performed deformations of the interface. The only possibility here is that some particles are present at the solution surface - even though the equilibrium surface tension measurements (Fig. 7a) do not evidence a measurable difference between solutions with and without particles for $c_p = 1\text{wt}\%$. If the contact angle is sufficiently modified after amine adsorption, the adsorption energy can be several times $k_B T$ and the particles will not desorb easily upon compression - at least at short time-scales. Estimations of particle contact angle are detailed in Appendix 3. The fact that the surface tension is not significantly affected by the particles is not a proof that the particles are not present at the surface, it just means that the surface pressure increase due to the particles is small, in line with the observation of disconnected patches at the surface. The surface pressure increases when the layer is compressed, likely because the domains containing particles get in contact with each other.

The hysteresis is limited for $c_a = 0.1\text{wt}\%$, but significantly increases at $c_a = 0.5\text{wt}\%$ and above as shown in Fig. 9. This is in line with the significant increase of amine adsorption on particles above the cac: $c_a = c_a^* = 0.5\text{wt}\%$.

6 Summary and discussion

Let us first discuss the low amine concentration region. Below the cac (c_a^*), binding of amines to the particle surface is quite limited. The amount of adsorbed particles at the liquid surface is small, explaining why foaming and foam stability are limited. Let us recall that the amine used is a short-chain surfactant, unable to stabilise foams alone.

Above the cac, cooperative amine adsorption occurs and foaming and foam stability increase until $c_a \sim 1\text{wt}\%$. This is accompanied by particle adsorption at the surface as evidenced by the investigations of the particle-laden air-water interfaces. The presence of the particles in the interfaces leads to reduced or "limited" coalescence, but does not influence measurably the coarsening. The dilational surface elastic modulus seems too small to suppress coarsening (the Gibbs criterion requires that $E > \gamma/2$ in order to fully suppress coarsening⁵²) and the particle layers at the interfaces seem to collapse easily (Fig. 7) in response to the stresses exerted by the coarsening process.

Further addition of amine ($c_a = 1.5 - 2.5\text{wt}\%$) leads to very stable foams in which coalescence is completely suppressed. Nevertheless, the lifetimes of the foams remain of the order of several days due to the presence of coarsening. The conclusion which must be drawn from this is that even though the particle layer seems solid-like at short time scales, it is not on long time scales. In order for the bubbles to shrink indefinitely during the coarsening process, the particles must desorb from the gas-liquid interface, even though adsorption energies are much higher than $k_B T$. One possible reason for this may be that physisorption of surfactants is reversible, hence providing the particles and the particle layers with the possibility to re-configure the surfactant organisation

at their surface. Liggieri et al. continue³² to find a very slow relaxation process upon investigations of mixed silica particle-surfactant layers, which they interpret as coming from an exchange dynamics between the two species. Another possibility could be that particles covered by surfactants more easily form multi-layers upon compression than pure particle systems.

Above $c_a^{**} = 2.5\text{wt}\%$, and in the low particle concentration limit ($c_p = 1\text{wt}\%$), the fast phase separation observed in bulk inhibits foaming. This is similar to the behaviour of nonionic surfactant foams, which are very stable just below the cloud point and destabilise above, when the solution starts to phase separate.

In contrast, at the high particle concentration limit ($c_p = 10\text{ wt}\%$), "superstable" foams are obtained in the microfluidic device, in which not only coalescence, but also coarsening are inhibited. Due to confinement effects gelation is probably faster in the thin films separating bubbles, which may account for the complete suppression of the three destabilisation mechanisms even when the complete gelation of the bulk aqueous phase is still in progress. However, further investigations are needed to understand the precise relative contributions of surface and bulk.

7 Conclusions

We have studied the foaming properties of mixtures of silica nanoparticles and *n*-amylamine using both simple hand shaking methods and more elaborate microfluidic techniques. This work is a natural continuation of previous investigations of the foaming^{12,22,53} and interfacial properties^{28,29,31,32} of aqueous dispersions of nano-particle-surfactant mixtures. Our work highlights the complexity of the synergetic effects between the particles and the surfactants, and their influence on the stability of the foams obtained from these complex mixtures. In particular, we have been able to show that by tuning carefully the concentration of both species, different regimes of foam stability can be accessed, in which one or more mechanisms of foam destabilisation are suppressed. Surprisingly to us, foams generated from silica particle-amine mixtures are superstable only when particle and surfactant concentrations are sufficient, otherwise coarsening persists. Whether foams from particlesurfactant mixtures coarsen or not seems to depend on the surfactant type used.²⁷ We have investigated in more detail mixtures of Ludox TMA and CTAB surfactants, but find the same general behaviour as for the Ludox-amine mixture. The fundamental reason behind these observations - and its contrast to the superstability of foams generated from chemically modified nano-particles - may be due to the presence of an additional relaxation process due to the physi-sorption of the surfactant onto the particles. Since the surfactants can not only slide along the particle surface, but also desorb from it, we believe that the concept of a finite and homogenous wetting angle of the particles with the gas-liquid interface has to be questioned for these systems. For example, the absence of a measurable surface tension change at low amine concentrations may be due to the surfac-

tants accumulating on one side of the particle, attaching it to the interface only via the hydrophobic surfactant tails. I.e. the particle remains fully in the water, whilst the surfactants attached to its surface stick out into the air - like a Janus-type particle. Also, the particle-laden interfaces of particle-surfactant mixtures seem to be much less resistant to compression than those of pure particle systems. Whilst the latter buckle, giving rise to the wellknown "crumpled" look of bubbles whose coarsening process has stopped, the first seem to form multilayers or expel particles quite easily from their interfaces.²⁷ I.e. the mechanical properties of pure particle systems and of particle-surfactant mixtures are very different. However, Binks et al. reported recently that a particular particle-surfactant mixture could produce superstable foams that do not coarsen even without bulk gelation.²² Future research therefore needs to establish the conditions a particlesurfactant mixture needs to fulfil in order to arrest coarsening. Another important difference between particle-surfactant mixtures and pure particle dispersions is that foams can be generated much more easily in the first case. For example, in the case of chemically modified, partially hydrophobic silica nano-particles^{21,52,54} high energy foaming techniques are required to bring the particles to the air-water interface. Hence, despite great efforts, we have never been able to reproducibly produce pure particle foams using microfluidic techniques. Particlesurfactant mixtures, in contrast, can be foamed very easily and with more "gentle" foaming techniques, such as microfluidic techniques. There remains, however, a marked difference between energetic and gentle foaming techniques, the latter requiring much higher particle concentrations to generate foams of comparable stability at short time scales. This may be due to the presence of energy barriers and different relaxation mechanisms in both systems. For example, charges are screened quite strongly in particle-surfactant mixtures and surfactant-coated particles may be more "slippery" and therefore arrange more easily close to and in the air-water surface. Since questions of foamability are very important in the hunt for superstable foams, such observations should be addressed more quantitatively in future research in order to better understand the key mechanism at play in the adsorption - and therefore foaming - dynamics.

Appendices

Appendix 1. Thermodynamics of the solutions

We have measured the pH of silica nanoparticle dispersions of different concentrations (1,5 and 10wt%) with increasing *n*-amylamine content (from 0.1 to 5wt%) as shown in Fig. 10. Significant consumption of *n*-amylamine, relative to the blanks ($c_p = 0\text{wt}\%$), is observed, such that the higher the particle concentration, the higher the *n*-amylamine consumption. However, when the pH values are plotted versus c_a/c_p as shown in the inset of Fig. 10, no scaling is seen, meaning that the association between particles and amine is not purely electrostatic.

Let us first discuss the solutions containing amine only. We have the dissociation equilibrium:

where the amine ion is designated by B^+ , $K_b = [\text{B}^+] \times [\text{OH}^-] / [\text{BOH}]$ and $\text{p}K_b = -\log K_b = 3.37$. The neutrality of the solution writes: $[\text{B}^+] + [\text{H}^+] = [\text{OH}^-] \approx [\text{B}^+]$, since the pH is basic. The total amine concentration is quite high, for instance 0.11 M for $c_a = 1\text{wt}\%$, and at the pH measured (Fig. 10), $[\text{B}^+] \ll [\text{BOH}] \sim C_a$, with C_a being the amine concentration in molar units. The pH of the solutions can therefore be easily calculated. For instance, for $c_a = 1\text{wt}\%$, $C_a = 0.11\text{M}$ and the calculated pH is 11.84, whereas the measured one is somewhat smaller, approximately 11.2. This is probably because the amine concentrations are very high and activities should be used instead of concentrations for these calculations. However, they allow us to account for the trend observed.

Let us now discuss the amine-particle dispersions. In basic solutions, silica is dissociated,⁵⁵ the silanol groups releasing H^+ ions in the dispersion:

with $\text{p}K_a = 7.5$. The equilibria involving further protonation occur only under extremely acidic conditions and can be disregarded here. We then have: $K_a = [\text{SiO}^-] [\text{H}^+] / [\text{SiOH}]$ and $[\text{SiO}^-] / [\text{SiOH}] = K_a / [\text{H}^+]$. The area per silanol group at the particle surface is about 0.2 nm^2 , but it is currently admitted that not all these groups are reactive and that the maximum charge density corresponds to an area of 0.32 nm^2 .⁵⁶ The manufacturer of the silica used quotes a specific area of $140 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ leading to a total silanol group concentration $[\text{SiO}^-] + [\text{SiOH}] = 7.3\text{mM}$ for $c_p = 1\text{wt}\%$. For $c_a = 1\text{wt}\%$, the pH is 11.2 (Fig. 10) and $[\text{H}^+] = 10^{-11.2}$. In order to have the activity of H^+ ions close to the particle surface, we can multiply this concentration by the factor $\beta = \exp(e\psi/k_B T)$, with ψ being the surface potential. With $\psi = 37\text{mV}$, the zeta potential value of Fig. 7, $\beta \sim 2$. Using now the acid equilibrium, we get: $[\text{SiO}^-] / [\text{SiOH}] = K_a / 2 [\text{H}^+] \sim 2500$. We can therefore assume that all the silanol groups are dissociated at the pH of this study (similar conclusions will be obtained for the other concentrations).

In the presence of particles the neutrality of the solution becomes: $[\text{B}^+] + [\text{H}^+] \approx [\text{B}^+] = [\text{OH}^-] + [\text{SiO}^-]$. At pH = 11.2, $[\text{OH}^-] = 10^{-2.8} = 1.6\text{mM}$ and $[\text{B}^+] = 8.9\text{mM}$. We can also use the base equilibrium for the amine, assuming that the initial $[\text{BOH}]$ is lowered by $[\text{SiO}^-]$, leading to $[\text{B}^+] = 23\text{mM}$. This is clearly inconsistent with the charge neutralisation condition. One could think that the value of $[\text{SiO}^-]$ is overestimated, but it is already negligible compared to $[\text{BOH}]$. The discrepancy could again come to the fact that we have neglected the differences between amine concentration and activity.

The charge per particle can be easily calculated from the silanol groups' concentration, leading to a charge per unit area of $3e \text{ nm}^{-2}$ or 0.5Cbm^{-2} . The

charge can also be estimated using the Grahame equation that relates the ionic concentration c_{ion} to the surface charge density:

$$\sigma = (8k_{\text{B}}TNc_{\text{ion}}\varepsilon)^{1/2} \sinh(e\Psi/2k_{\text{B}}T)$$

where N is the Avogadro number and ε the dielectric constant of the solvent. We have neglected here the curvature term that involves the product κR , with κ^{-1} being the Debye length, equal to 3 nm for an ionic strength of 10 mM. For a surface potential of -37mV , $c_{\text{ion}} \sim 9\text{mM}$ and $\varepsilon = 80\varepsilon_0$ (with ε_0 being the dielectric constant of vacuum), we get $\sigma \sim 3 \times 10^{-4}\text{Cbm}^{-2}$. This number is considerably smaller than the value found above from the pH. This is probably due to the fact that the Grahame equation takes into account the screening of particle ions, very important here due to the high ionic strength. The zeta potential is not the true surface potential, since it includes counterions moving with the particle, the true surface potential being certainly higher.

If we finally consider the case of larger particle concentrations, even for 10wt% particles, the concentration $[\text{SiO}^-]$ will rise to 73 mM, still lower than the initial amine concentration in the cooperative binding regime and at the cmc ($\sim 280\text{mM}$).

It is clearly impossible to go further than these simple estimations. The amine activity is not known and the zeta potential cannot reliably be used. Complete calculations are out of reach from this description, which nevertheless gives some orders of magnitude useful to understanding the phenomena occurring in the mixed dispersions.

Appendix 2. Stability of nano-particle- *n*-amylamine dispersions

The stability of the silica nano-particle dispersions ($c_{\text{p}} = 1\text{wt}\%$) is significantly altered by the addition of *n*-amylamine at concentrations $c_{\text{a}} \geq c_{\text{a}}^{**} \sim 2 - 3\text{wt}\%$, for which phase separation is observed as shown in Fig. 11: the kinetics of the phase separation is quite fast (i.e. 30 min) for c_{a} close to c_{a}^{**} or slightly larger but it occurs at very long times (i.e. 5 days) for $c_{\text{a}} \geq c_{\text{a}}^{***} \sim 5\text{wt}\%$.

Appendix 3. Particle contact angle

As discussed in Section 7, we believe that the concept of a finite contact angle of surfactant-coated particles needs to be treated with great care. However, since we have the data available, we apply here an approach suggested by Clint and Taylor⁵⁷ to estimate the particle contact angle at the air-water interface from the surface pressure Π -surface area A compression isotherms as shown in Fig. 12a: firstly we have estimated the cross-sectional area of the particle at the so-called gel point, A_{g} , which corresponds to the area at which a close-packed particle layer is formed; secondly we have determined the number of particles

adsorbed at the air-water interface, $N_p = A_g/A_p$, with A_p being the surface area of a single silica particle ($R \approx 20$ nm; $A_p \approx 5 \times 10^{-15}$ m²); finally we have obtained the particle contact angle, θ , from the work required to remove a particle from the surface cohesive layer using the expression derived by Clint and Taylor,⁵⁷ $\Pi_c A'_c = \gamma \pi R^2 (1 \pm \cos \theta)^2$, with A'_{col} being the particle crosssectional area at the collapse, obtaining by dividing the layer collapse area A_{col} by the number of particles, N_p , and with Π_{col} being the collapse pressure.

The positive or negative sign in the bracket indicates whether the particle is removed from the interface towards the upper or lower phase, respectively. The procedure cannot be applied to $c_a = 0.1$ wt% because the layer in this case collapses at smaller areas than the ones available within the Langmuir trough, but we present the obtained results for $c_a = 0.5$ and 1wt% in Table 1 and Fig. 12b.

In the mixtures with particles, surfactant molecules will be removed from the bulk phase due to particle coverage, the others remaining free in solution. It is very difficult to estimate the actual bulk amine concentration, so we used surface tension ranges between 72mNm⁻¹ and the surface tension of pure amine solutions. When particles arrive at the interface, they must rearrange in the formed surfactant monolayer, finding less available area when c_a is larger (at constant c_p). Thus they collapse at larger area and higher pressure. In addition, the gel point area is found to be smaller in the case of the smaller c_a . The obtained contact angles are close to 90°, leading to very high adsorption energies ($\sim 10^4 k_B T$), which allows for highlighting the irreversible particle surface attachment. The strength of the electrostatic binding between the positively charged surfactant and the negatively charged particles is of the same order of magnitude as that of the typical attachment energies of surfactants at the air-water interface ($\sim k_B T$), thus we cannot discard at this point surfactant rearrangements between the particle surface and the air-water interface.

One may expect that the higher the amine concentration the higher the hydrophobicity of the particle and thus one should trust the recessing contact angles, which indicates that the particles are moving towards the upper phase upon collapse leading to multilayer formation, instead of desorption.

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Fig. 1 (a) Schematic illustration of the microfluidic device for production of particle-stabilized foams. Three syringe pumps control the particle-amine ratio and concentration. Liquid and air encounters in a T-junction, after a delay line of approximately 15 cm, producing highly monodisperse bubbles. (b) Optical microscope image showing generation of monodisperse bubbles at typical flow rates of liquid and air of 40 and 60 mL h⁻¹, respectively. The inner diameter of the capillary after the T-junction is 170 μm .

Fig. 2 Images of foams generated by hand shaking dispersions containing 1,5 and 10wt% particles and increasing *n*-amylamine content, taken (a) immediately after preparation and (b) 24 hours afterwards.

Fig. 3 Foam height (normalised by the maximum height recorded) after hand shaking a 1wt²% particle dispersion as a function of *n*-amylamine concentration. The dashed line is a visual guide for the data.

Fig. 4 (a) Aspect of foams generated using microfluidics for 10wt% particle dispersions and increasing amine concentration. Microfluidic-generated bubbles are collected in vials during 45 s and images were taken immediately after filling in order to evaluate foamability of the system. (b) Foam evolution with time for $c_a = 2$ and 3wt%. (c) Foam height (left scale) and foam half life time (right scale) as a function of c_a . Open and solid circles represent the results obtained in two independent experiments to show reproducibility and dashed lines are visual guides for the data.

Concent.		Foamability	Foam stability	Regimes
C_p (wt%)	C_a (wt%)			
< 5	< 3	COALESCENCE	COALESCENCE	
5	< 1	 LIMITED COALESCENCE	COARSENING	I Limited Coalescence AND Coarsening
10	2	 COARSENING (gelled interfaces)	II NO Coalescence BUT Coarsening	
10	3	 NO COARSENING (here foam after 2 years)	III NO Coalescence NO Coarsening	

Fig. 5 Monodisperse foams obtained at various c_a and two particle concentrations, 5 and 10wt%. For $c_p < 5\text{wt}\%$ we were not able to create foams in the microfluidic device in the defined range of amine concentrations for which the mixture foams by hand-shaking ($c_a < 3\text{wt}\%$), evolving by coalescence. For $c_a = 1\text{wt}\%$, limited coalescence is observed at $c_p = 5\text{wt}\%$ while almost no coalescence is noticed at $c_p = 10\text{wt}\%$. In the last case, coarsening is still present. At higher amine concentration, coarsening is also stopped, accompanied with bulk gelation. All bubble sizes are around $500\mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 6 (a) Variation of the zeta-potential of the dispersions containing 1wt% silica nano-particles as a function of *n*-amyamine concentration (right scale). The divisor line at $\zeta = -30$ mV is used as a visual line to separate stable from unstable dispersions. The pH values of the corresponding dispersions have been included in the graph (left scale). (b) Variation of the hydrodynamic diameter of the aggregates present in the different dispersions. The amine concentrations separating the different stability regimes are c_a^* , which represents the critical aggregation concentration above which amine adsorption onto the particle surface becomes cooperative and c_a^{**} , above which flocculation starts leading to the phase separation of the dispersion.

Fig. 7 (a) Comparison of the equilibrium surface tension of *n*-amylamine solutions in the absence and presence of 1 and 10wt% of silica nano-particles. (b) BAM image showing the presence of solid domains at the air-water interface due to particle adsorption for an aqueous dispersion of $c_a = 1\text{wt}\%$ and $c_p = 10\text{wt}\%$ at $\gamma_0 = 35.4\text{mNm}^{-1}$. The right image shows the domain of the left image which was fractured using a needle, evidencing its solid character.

Fig. 8 Time evolution of (a) surface tension and of (b) surface compression elastic modulus, E . The surface tension curves correspond to $c_a = 0.5$ and 1wt% and $c_p = 10$ wt%. The curves for the solutions without particles are also shown. The elasticity measurements shown were made with the same solutions with applied sinusoidal deformation of amplitude 1.5% and frequency 0.2 Hz (without particles, $E = 0$).

Fig. 9 Surface pressure Π -surface area A compression/expansion isotherms of amine/particle mixtures containing $c_p = 1$ wt% and increasing n -amylamine content: $c_a =$ (left) 0.1 , (middle) 0.5 and (right) 1wt%.

Fig. 10 pH variation as a function of n -amylamine concentration for three dispersions with increasing silica nanoparticle concentration, 1, 5 and 10wt%, exhibiting significant consumption of base as compared to the blank (absence of particles), which points out that silanol dissociation reaction has taken place. Inset: the observed pH variation cannot be rescaled when representing the data as a function of the n -amylamine:particle ratio.

Fig. 11 Images of foams generated by hand shaking dispersions containing 1wt% particles and increasing *n*-amylamine content, taken immediately after shaking and 30 min, 2 h, 1 day and 5 days afterwards (from top to bottom).

Fig. 12 (a) Example of the estimation of the gel point A_g , as well as the collapse area and pressure (A_{col}, Π_{col}) from the compression $\Pi - A$ isotherm of the surfactant/particle mixture containing $c_p = 1\text{wt}\%$ and $c_a = 1\text{wt}\%$. Such values are used to determine the particle contact angle θ measured through the water. (b) Advancing and recessing contact angles for the range of possible surface tension values.